

COMPANY PRODUCTIVITY DESIGN TO INCREASE COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract

Companies have an important role in increasing economic turnover. Because in general, the development of an increasingly widespread company, it proves that there is good productivity and vice versa. Therefore, it is necessary to measure productivity and design a productivity improvement system and factors that affect productivity to find out at what level the company's productivity is the attainment and the factors that affect productivity. The research was conducted at PT. Arc Inti Indo Panah which is engaged in the soy sauce industry located in Langkat Regency. This research will explain efforts to increase company productivity in the face of increasingly competitive competition. The study concluded that the company's productivity level decreased (fluctuated), the utilization of labor still tends to be inefficient, and capacitation can be increased by 27.25%. It is concluded that the leadership and ability of employees greatly affect the level of productivity of the company.

Keywords: Productivity Design, Company, Leadership, Improving Competitiveness

INTRODUCTION

Increasing productivity can be pursued through increasing output and input, because by increasing the output produced and suppressing the input used to produce the output it will produce a positive value (Sumanth, 1982). In the current era of globalization, the issue of increasing productivity has become a major parameter for every institution to win the competition in the face of rapid environmental changes, so productivity is an important element for the existence of an institution. In general, productivity is the ratio between output and input. Productivity is a measure of the ability of one unit of input to produce output. Inputs are production resources, namely: labor, materials, energy, capital, production costs and equipment costs (Plag, 2020). While the output is the total or the sum of the values of all the results and all other income earned in a certain period.

In the private sector or business organizations, the problem of increasing productivity has always been the main thing, this is due to the increasing demands on the quality of the products produced. Good product quality is an important instrument towards competitive advantage (Kuehn, & Day, 1962). At the enterprise level, productivity measurement is mainly used as a management tool to analyze and promote production efficiency. Productivity is a statement that shows the efforts of employees who are supported by high motivation and employee abilities. Significantly increased productivity means showing good performance so that it becomes feedback for business continuity.

The motivation of a worker to work productively is something that is very complicated because such motivation involves individual and organizational factors. Work productivity is also determined by the ability of an employee in carrying out a job. The workability of an employee is said to be good if he can complete the task successfully, effectively and efficiently. An employee can achieve satisfactory performance in carrying out his work depending on his abilities. According to Gomes (2000), a highly capable employee may only need a little effort to achieve very high performance, on the other hand, other employees with low abilities may have to work harder to produce better performance.

Reliable leadership is needed by organizations to achieve goals. So success in achieving group goals is highly dependent on the role of the leader (Hughes et al., 1993). The smarter the leader in carrying out his role, of course, the faster the goals of the organization can be achieved. The responsibility of a leader is to encourage employees towards the achievement of useful goals. As the company PT. Arc Inti Indo Panah, which is engaged in the soy sauce industry, located in Langkat Regency, seeks to increase the company's productivity in the face of increasingly competitive competition. However, there is a phenomenon that indicates a decrease in employee productivity which is reflected in the level of employee discipline, namely often not coming to work, employee turnover of 3%, and low development of selling areas, causing the production process to be discontinuous, product innovation is relatively low and quality control is a relatively rare product.

Until now, the company has never measured productivity, so it has not been able to implement a productivity program properly. In this regard, it is necessary to measure productivity and design a productivity improvement system along with identifying the factors that affect productivity to know at what level the company's productivity is achieving and the factors that affect productivity so that the company can use it to determine strategies for improving competitiveness in the future. Because various indicators refer to productivity such as the level of discipline of employees (often absent), and labor turnover on average of 3% per year, and expansion of low-selling areas causes the production process to be discontinuous which indicates that productivity is still low.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research was carried out in the form of a survey using an explanatory research approach, namely research that explains the relationship between the input variables used to the resulting output. The research was conducted at PT. Indo Arrow Binjai Core Bow. To determine the accuracy of the questionnaire measuring instrument, in this study it is necessary to do a reliability test. A measuring instrument is said to be reliable if it is sufficiently accurate, stable and consistent in measuring an object. Reliability measurement can be done more than once at different times.

The reliability test was carried out using the Cronbach Alpha formula:

$$r = \frac{k}{k-1} \left[1 - \frac{\sum \sigma_i^2}{\sigma^2} \right] \dots\dots\dots(V.1)$$

- where: r = reliability coefficient
- k = number of questions
- σ_i^2 = question item variant
- σ^2 = test score variance

If the results of the calculation of a construct or variable obtained Cronbach's Alpha correlation value above 0.60 then the questionnaire instrument designed is declared reliable (reliable). The research population is all 192 employees of the company. The number of samples (n) was determined based on the Slovin formula with a tolerable error rate (e) of 5%.

$$n = N/(1+N (e)^2) \dots\dots\dots(V.3)$$

$$n = 192/(1+ 192 (5\%) = 130 \text{ person}$$

Validity test

A validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. This study uses a construct validity measuring instrument (construct validity). As it is known that the construct is the framework of the concept, therefore this validity emphasizes the preparation of questions for questions or the instrument as a whole based on the operational clarity of the definition, which details the elements of the variables studied. In this research, correlation is done between the indicator and the variable it measures (total score). The formula used is as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{\{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}} \dots\dots\dots(V.2)$$

Information :

- n = number of samples
- X = item score X
- Y = item score Y

To determine the validity, statistically the correlation number obtained (r_{count}) must be compared with the critical number of the product moment correlation table (r_{table}) at a significance level of 5%. If the correlation number obtained is above the critical number, it means the indicator is valid.

Data Collection Methods and Models

The implementation of data collection was carried out using a survey method for calculating the productivity index data and using a questionnaire list instrument to identify factors that affect productivity. A research instrument is a tool used to measure the observed natural and social phenomena (Creswel, 2014). Because this research variable involves attitudes or perceptions that are individual and subjective, the questionnaire instrument is used to measure the research variables. The questionnaires used are open and closed in which the contents of the questions consist of 6 kinds of variables, each variable consists of X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , X_4 , X_5 , and X_6 . Respondents were asked to fill in a number (score) 1-5 for each question item. Responses to the questions posed are expressed on an ordinal scale based on a Likert scale for five answer options, namely: the most positive leading answer is given a score of 5 and the most negative leading answer is given a score of 1 as follows: score 5: Strongly agree (SS), score 4: agree (S), score 3: disagree (KS), score 2: disagree (TS), score 1: strongly disagree (STS): 0

The data obtained is processed by following the following steps:

- 1) Calculating Standard Time with the aim of finding the standard time for completion of work, to find out how many real workers and production capacity are
- 2) Tabulate the cost of each input, namely: labor costs, material costs, energy and capital costs and income (output) in Rupiah.
- 3) Calculating Partial Productivity
- 4) Calculating Total Productivity and Total Factor Productivity
- 5) Calculating Productivity Index (IP) based on constant price (%)
- 6) Calculating Profitability Index (IPF) based on current prices
- 7) Calculating the Price Improvement Index (IPH).
- 8) Identify factors that affect productivity by using statistics, namely multiple regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Calculation of Standard Time (Standard)

The purpose of measuring the standard time (standard): a) to get the standard time of completion of work, b) to get the number of workers and real production capacity. Standard time is the time it takes a normal worker to complete a job in the best work system. To calculate the standard time, it is necessary to first know the flow of the production process for making soy sauce. The time measurement is carried out directly, namely where the work is carried out on several populations for each part of the process by using a stopwatch. The measurement of time is assumed that the work method is standard, the production process runs normally per shift of 7 effective working hours, and the output is calculated in units of expansion.

Several steps are taken to calculate the standard time: a) Measuring cycle time, b) Data adequacy test, c) Calculating standard deviation, d) Data uniformity test, e) Calculating the normal time, and f) Correcting the number of workers. To calculate the normal time, it is necessary to add an adjustment factor (rating factor). Adjustment factors according to Westinghouse consist of a) Skills, b) Business, c) Working conditions and d) Consistency (Sutalaksana, 1982). To calculate the standard time added with the allowance (allowance). The amount of allowance is given based on the influencing factors consisting of 8 types: a) Energy expended, b) Work attitude, c) Work movement, d) Eye fatigue, e) Temperature conditions, f) Atmospheric conditions, g) Environmental conditions environment and h) Personal needs.

Result of Validity Test and Instrument Reliability Test

The instrument that will be used to collect data must be tested first for the level of validity and reliability so that it can be seen that the instrument used is valid as an appropriate data collection tool. Measurement of validity and reliability by testing the questionnaire to 30 respondents.

a. Validity Test Results

Validity shows the level of ability of the research instrument, measures what is to be measured and can reveal data from the variables studied appropriately (Shepard, 1993). The validity test uses the Product Moment correlation technique by correlating the score of each item with the total score. The instrument is declared valid if the Product Moment correlation value (r_{count}) is greater than the value of the r table at the real level = 5%. The results of the validity test can be seen in the following table,

Table 1: Validity Test Results

Variable	Question points	Value of r_{count}	Value r_{Table}	Information
X ₁	X _{1.1.1}	0,700	0,404	Valid
	X _{1.1.2}	0,613		Valid
	X _{1.1.3}	0,743		Valid
	X _{1.2.1}	0,660		Valid
	X _{1.2.2}	0,853		Valid
	X _{1.2.3}	0,727		Valid
X ₂	X _{2.1.1}	0,748	0,404	Valid
	X _{2.1.2}	0,690		Valid
	X _{2.2.1}	0,642		Valid
	X _{2.2.2}	0,617		Valid
X ₃	X _{3.1.1}	0,564	0,404	Valid
	X _{3.1.2}	0,600		Valid
	X _{3.1.3}	0,569		Valid
	X _{3.2.1}	0,626		Valid
	X _{3.2.2}	0,714		Valid
X ₄	X _{4.1.1}	0,621	0,404	Valid
	X _{4.2.1}	0,484		Valid
	X _{4.2.2}	0,839		Valid
X ₅	X _{5.1.1}	0,624	0,404	Valid
	X _{5.1.2}	0,541		Valid
	X _{5.2.1}	0,524		Valid
X ₆	X _{6.1.1}	0,405	0,404	Valid
	X _{6.1.2}	0,603		Valid
	X _{6.2.1}	0,666		Valid
Y	Y _{1.1}	0,576	0,404	Valid
	Y _{1.2}	0,571		Valid
	Y _{2.1}	0,782		Valid
	Y _{2.2}	0,648		Valid

Source: primary data processed

From the results of the validity test, it appears that the score of each question item is significantly correlated with the total score, it is shown that the correlation coefficient value of

each item is greater than the table correlation value at a significant level of 5%, thus the questions used are valid. Or in other words, the research instrument that has been carried out, it is found that the count value of each instrument tested is greater than the r_{table} value ($r_{count} > r_{table}$), where the r_{table} value in this study is 0.404.

b. Reliability Test Results

Reliability is the level of reliability of a measurement. Measurements that have high reliability are those that are able to provide consistent measurement results (Kuder & Richardson, 1937). In this study, the reliability test used the Alpha Cronbach method, where the instrument was declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value reached at least 0.6 (Nurgiyantoro, 2000). The results of the reliability test are in the following table,

Table 2: Reliability Test Results

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Reliability Limit	Information
X ₁	0,774	0,6	reliable
X ₂	0,764	0,6	reliable
X ₃	0,738	0,6	reliable
X ₄	0,748	0,6	reliable
X ₅	0,644	0,6	reliable
X ₆	0,644	0,6	reliable
Y	0,734	0,6	reliable

Source: primary data processed

From the results of calculations using SPSS 16.00 software, Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than the reliability limit of 0.6 (Nurgiyantoro, 2000), meaning that the instrument used is reliable.

Description of Research Variables

a. Leadership (X₁)

The results of the leadership variable questionnaire analysis (X₁) are in the following table:

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Leadership Variables (X₁)

Butir Pertan yaan	Kategori										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
X _{1.1.1}	1	0,77	0	0	45	34,62	60	46,15	24	18,46	130
X _{1.1.2}	1	0,77	0	0	42	32,31	16	12,31	71	54,62	130
X _{1.1.3}	0	0	1	0,77	15	11,54	80	61,54	34	26,15	130
X _{1.2.1}	1	0,77	0	0	10	7,69	95	73,08	24	18,46	130
X _{1.2.2}	0	0	0	0	41	31,54	64	49,23	25	19,23	130
X _{1.2.3}	0	0	1	0,77	12	9,23	76	58,46	41	31,54	130

Source: primary data processed

Information :

- X_{1.1.1} : Task directions
- X_{1.1.2} : Solution to problem
- X_{1.1.3} : Decision-making
- X_{1.2.1} : Problem analysis
- X_{1.2.2} : Communication
- X_{1.2.3} : Supervision

From Table 3, the responses of respondents about their superiors explaining the direction of the task as many as 24 people (18.46%) said they strongly agreed, 60 people (46.15%) agreed, 45 people (34.62%) disagreed and 1 person (77%) said strongly disagree. In respondents' responses that the leader provided problem-solving 71 people (54.62%) said strongly agreed, 16 people (12.31%) said agreed, 42 people (32.31%) said they did not agree and 1 person (0.77%) strongly disagree. Respondents' responses that leaders always use decision making in task planning were 34 people (26.15%) said they strongly agreed, 80 people (61.54%) said they agreed, 15 people (11.54%) said they did not agree, 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses that the leadership used problem analysis in task monitoring were 24 people (18.46%) said they strongly agreed, 95 people (73.08 %) said they agreed, 10 people (7.69%) said they did not agree, and 1 person (0.77%) said strongly disagree.

Respondents responded that the leader always communicates with employees in carrying out daily tasks, the results obtained 25 people (19.23%) say strongly agree, 64 people (49.23%) say agree, and 41 people (31.54%) say disagree. Respondents' responses that the leadership always supervises the implementation of work, 41 people (31.54%) said they strongly agreed, 76 people (58.46%) said they agreed, 12 people (9.23%) said they did not agree, 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree.

b. Motivation (X₂)

The results of the questionnaire analysis on the motivation variable (X₂) in Table 4

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Motivational Variables (X₂)

Question Items	Category										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
X _{2.1.1}	0	0	1	0,77	9	6,92	87	66,92	33	25,38	130
X _{2.1.2}	0	0	0	0	32	24,62	12	9,23	86	66,15	130
X _{2.2.1}	0	0	1	0,77	8	6,15	76	58,46	45	34,62	130
X _{2.2.2}	0	0	1	0,77	40	30,77	41	31,54	48	36,92	130

Source: primary data processed

Information :

X_{2.1.1} : Giving rewards and punishment

X_{2.1.2} : Provision of facilities

X_{2.2.1} : Promotion system

X_{2.2.2} : Training and capacity building

In respondents' responses that the reward and punishment system must be firm and consistent 33 people (25.38%) said they strongly agree, 87 people (66.92%) agree, 9 people (6.92%) disagree, and 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses so far the company has provided attractive work facilities of 86 people (66.15%) said they strongly agreed, 12 people (9.23%) said they agreed, and 32 people (24.62%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses that the company provides a promotion system must be clear to employees 45 people (34.62%) said strongly agree, 76 people (58.46%) said they agreed, 8 people (6.15%) said they did not agree, and 1 person (0.77%) disagree. Respondents' responses that the company has been holding training and employee capacity development are 48 people (36.92%) saying they strongly agree, 41 people (31.54%) say they agree, 40 people (30.77%) say they don't agree, 1 people (0.77%) said they did not agree.

c. Work environment (X₃)

The results of the questionnaire analysis on environmental variables (X₃) are in Table 5.

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of Work Environment Variables (X₃)

Question Items	Category										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
X _{3.1.1}	0	0	1	0,77	25	19,23	70	53,85	34	26,15	130
X _{3.1.2}	1	0,77	1	0,77	18	13,85	57	43,85	53	40,77	130
X _{3.1.3}	0	0	1	0,77	31	23,85	48	36,92	50	38,46	130
X _{3.2.1}	0	0	0	0	25	19,23	68	52,31	37	28,46	130
X _{3.2.2}	0	0	1	0,77	17	13,08	73	56,15	39	30	130

Source: primary data processed

Information :

X_{3.1.1} : Workplace temperature

X_{3.1.2} : Explanation

X_{3.1.3} : Noise

X_{3.2.1} : Smells

X_{3.2.2} : Equipment or work aids

On average, respondents stated that they strongly agree that the workplace temperature is still not comfortable by 34 people (26.15%), saying they agree with 70 people (53.85%), saying they don't agree with 25 people (19.23%), and said they disagreed by 1 person (0.77%). Respondents' responses that the lighting in the work area is still not appropriate as many as 53 people (40.77%) said strongly agree, 57 people (43.85%) said they agreed, 18 people (13.85%) said they did not agree, 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree, 1 person (0.77%) said they also strongly disagreed. Respondents' responses to the noise level in the workplace are still quite disturbing work concentration as many as 50 people (38.46%) said they strongly agree, 48 people (36.92%) said they agreed, 31 people (23.85%) said they did not agree, and 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree.

Respondents' responses to odours were still quite disturbing while working, 37 people (28.46%) said they strongly agreed, 68 people (52.31%) said they agreed, and 25 people (19.23%) said they did not agree. equipment or work aids are still lacking in the workplace 39 people (30%) strongly agree, 73 people (56.15%) agree, 17 people (13.08%) disagree, and 1 person (0.77%) doesn't agree.

d. Wages (X₄)

The results of the questionnaire analysis on the salary variable (X₄) are in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Frequency Distribution of Salary Variables (X₄)

Question Items	Category										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
X _{4.1.1}	0	0	1	0,77	25	1 9,23	70	53,85	34	2 6,15	130
X _{4.2.1}	0	0	1	0,77	19	1 4,62	77	59,23	33	2 5,38	130
X _{4.2.2}	0	0	0	0	52	40	33	25,38	45	3 4,62	130

Source: primary data processed

Information :

X_{4.1.1} : Conformity with expectations

X_{4.2.1} : Based on work

X_{4.2.2} : Fair and transparent

Respondents' responses that the amount of salary will affect the level of productivity were 34 people (26.15%) said they strongly agreed, 70 people (53.85%) said they agreed, 25 people (19.23%) said they did not agree, 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses that the punctuality of work will affect the salary to be received were 33 people (25.38%) said they strongly agreed, 77 people (59.23%) said they agreed, 19 people (14.62%) said they did not agree, and 1 person (0.77%) said they disagreed. Respondents' responses that the salary pattern would affect work productivity were 45 people (34.62%) said they strongly agreed, 33 people (25.38%) said they agreed, and 52 people (40%) say disagree.

e. Ability (X₅)

The results of the questionnaire on the ability variable (X₅) are in Table 7 below

Table 7: Frequency Distribution of Ability Variables (X₅)

Question Items	Category										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	F	%	
X _{5.1.1}	0	0	1	0,77	25	19,23	79	60,77	25	19,23	130
X _{5.1.2}	1	0,77	0	0	50	38,46	20	15,38	59	45,38	130
X _{5.2.1}	0	0	1	0,77	20	15,38	75	57,69	34	26,15	130

Source: primary data processed

Information:

X_{5.1.1}: Work mastery

X_{5.1.2}: Task load

X_{5.2.1}: Contribution of energy and thoughts

Respondents' responses to mastery of work can carry out their duties well by 25 people (19.23%) said they strongly agree, 79 people (60.77%) said they agreed, 25 people (19.23%) said they did not agree, and only 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses to the given task load could be completed well by 59 people (45.38%) said they strongly agreed, 20 people (15.38%) said they agreed, 50 people (38, 46%) said they did not agree, 1 person (0.77%) said they strongly disagreed. Respondents' responses that work always contributed to both energies and thoughts 34 people (26.15%) said they strongly agreed, 75 people (57, 69%) agree, 20 people (15.38%) disagree, and 1 person (0.77%) disagree.

f. Work Discipline (X₆)

The results of the questionnaire analysis of the work discipline variable (X₆) are in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Frequency Distribution of Work Discipline Variables (X₆)

Question Items	Category										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
X _{6.1.1}	0	0	1	0,77	26	20	72	55,38	31	2 3,85	130
X _{6.1.2}	0	0	1	0,77	9	6,92	86	66,15	34	2 6,15	130
X _{6.2.1}	0	0	2	1,54	36	27,69	50	38,46	42	3 2,31	130

Source: primary data processed

Information :

X_{6.1.1} : Presence

X_{6.1.2} : Use of time

X_{6.2.1} : Target achievement

Respondents' responses to attendance when arriving and leaving on time by the established regulations were 31 people saying strongly agree, 72 people (55.38%) said strongly agree, 26 people (20%) said they did not agree and only 1 person (0,74%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses that the optimal use of time so that the work is used as optimally as possible so that the work can be completed on time as many as 34 people (26.15%) said strongly agree, 86 people (66.15%) said agreed, 9 people (6.92 %) said they did not agree, and 1 person (0.77%) said they did not agree. Respondents' responses to the achievement of targets trying to carry out work in accordance with existing procedures so that it can be completed according to a set schedule of 42 people (32.31%) said strongly agree, 50 people (38.46%) said agreed, 36 people (27.69 %) said they did not agree, 2 people (1.54%) said they did not agree.

g. Work productivity (Y)

The results of the questionnaire analysis on productivity (Y) are shown in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Frequency Distribution of Work Productivity Variables (Y)

Question Items	Category										Total
	(STS)		(TS)		(KS)		(S)		(SS)		
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%	
Y _{1.1}	1	0,77	0	0	45	34,62	56	43,08	28	21,54	130
Y _{1.2}	1	0,77	0	0	7	5,38	104	80	18	13,85	130
Y _{2.1}	0	0	1	0,77	43	33,08	13	10	73	56,15	130
Y _{2.2}	0	0	0	0	44	33,85	62	47,69	24	18,46	130

Source: primary data processed

Information :

Y_{1.1} : Production quantity

Y_{1.2} : Production cost

Y_{2.1} : Effectiveness and efficiency

Y_{2.2} : Target and realization

Increased work productivity is the expected result by taking into account each of the above factors. From the results of research conducted on 130 company respondents, the average employee strongly agrees with the amount of production as a form of assessment of productivity as many as 28 people (21.54%) say strongly agree, 56 people (43.08%) say agree, 45 people (34.62%) said they did not agree, and 1 person (0.77%) said they strongly disagreed. Respondents' responses to production costs affect the accuracy of work or being able to do work

in accordance with the expected target as many as 18 people (13.85%) said strongly agree, 104 people (80%) said agreed, 7 people (5.38%) disagreed, and 1 person (0.775) strongly disagrees. Respondents' responses to effectiveness and efficiency are factors for achieving work targets 73 people (56.15%) say strongly agree, 13 people (10%) agree, 43 people (33.08%) disagree, and 1 person (0.77%)) don't agree. Respondents' responses to the target and realization are factors that support the achievement of the target, 24 people (18.46%) said they strongly agreed, 62 people (47.69%) said they agreed, and 44 people (33.85%) said they did not agree.

Regression Analysis Results

To analyze the data in identifying factors that affect productivity using Multiple Linear Regression, namely to analyze the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). The results of the regression analysis can be seen in Table 10. The effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable was tested with a significance level of = 5%.

Table 10: Summary of Regression Analysis Results

Variable	F _{count}	F _{table}	Information	B (Coefficient of Regression)	t _{count}	Sig.	t _{table}	Information
Leadership (X ₁)	112.401	1,39	Whole Factor Take effect Significant To Productivity (F _{count} > F _{table})	1,030	18,358	0,172	1,984	Take effect significant
Motivation (X ₂)				0,039	0,921	0,000		Not Take effect significant
Environment Work (X ₃)				-0,066	-1,511	0,359		Not Significantly influential
Wages (X ₄)				-0,019	-0,500	0,133		Not Significantly
Ability (X ₅)				0,103	2,676	0,618		Berp significant effect
Disiplin (X ₆)				-0,023	-0,518	0,008		No Significant effect

Source: Primary data processed

From the calculation results, the results of multiple linear regression analysis are obtained:

$$Y = (-0,319) + 1,030X_1 + 0,039X_2 + (-0,066) X_3 + (-0,019) X_4 + 0,103X_5 + (-0,023) X_6$$

$$Y = 1,030X_1 + 0,039X_2 - 0,066X_3 - 0,019X_4 + 0,103X_5 - 0,023X_6 - 0,319$$

a. Test Model

At the 95% confidence level (α = 5%) and df = 6:124 the F_{table} value = 1.39 while the F arithmetic value = 112.401 so that F_{count} > F_{table} with a significant value of 0.0000 which is smaller than 0.05. It means that the independent variables of leadership (X₁), motivation (X₂), work environment (X₃), salary (X₄), ability (X₅) and work discipline (X₆) can explain variations in employee productivity, thus the regression model can be used as a good estimator in this

study. The variables of leadership, motivation, work environment, salary, ability and discipline can explain employee productivity variables by 84.6% ($R^2 = 0.846$), the remaining 15.4% is explained by other variables not included in this research.

b. Hypothesis Test Results

1. Hypothesis Test Results I (Uji F)

Testing the first hypothesis with the F test where the calculated F value is 112.401 while the 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 5\%$) and $df = 6:124$ is obtained by the F table = 1.39 so that $F_{count} > F_{table}$ with a significant value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05, it was tested that leadership (X_1), motivation (X_2), work environment (X_3), salary (X_4), ability (X_5) and work discipline (X_6) had a significant effect on employee productivity (X_6). Y), thus hypothesis I is accepted.

2. Hasil Uji Hipotesis II (Uji t)

Testing the second hypothesis with the t-test is to test the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable (employee productivity), and then compare the regression coefficients between the significant independent variables.

a. Leadership (X_1)

The leadership regression coefficient (b_1) of (1.030) shows the leadership variable has a positive effect on employee productivity, the better leadership will lead to an increase in employee productivity. The results of the analysis obtained the value of $t_{count} 18.358 > t_{table} 1.984$, thus partially leadership has a significant effect on productivity (Y).

b. Motivation (X_2)

The regression coefficient of motivation (b_2) of (0.039) shows that the motivation variable has a negative effect on employee productivity, the better the motivation will not lead to an increase in employee productivity. The results of the analysis obtained the value of $t_{arithmetic} 0.921 < t_{table} 1.984$ thus partially motivation does not have a significant effect on employee productivity (Y).

c. Work environment (X_3)

The regression coefficient of the work environment (b_3) of (-.066) shows that the work environment variable has a positive effect on employee productivity, the better work environment will lead to an increase in employee productivity. The results of the analysis obtained the value of $t_{count} -1.511 < t_{table} 1.984$, thus partially the work environment has no significant effect on employee productivity (Y).

d. Wages (X_4)

The salary regression coefficient (b_4) of (-0.019) shows the salary variable hurts employee productivity, the better the salary will not cause an increase in employee productivity. The results of the analysis obtained the value of $t_{arithmetic} -0.500 < t_{table} 1.984$ thus partially salary has no significant effect on productivity (Y).

e. Ability (X_5)

The ability regression coefficient (b_5) of (0.103) indicates the ability variable has a positive effect on productivity. The better the ability will lead to increased productivity. The results of the analysis obtained the value of $t_{\text{count}} 2,676 > t_{\text{table}} 1,984$, thus partially ability has a significant effect on employee productivity (Y).

f. Work discipline (X_6)

The regression coefficient of work discipline (b_6) of (-0.023) indicates that the work discipline variable has a negative effect on productivity. Better work discipline will lead to increased productivity. The results of the analysis obtained the value of $t_{\text{count}} -0.518 > t_{\text{table}} 1.984$, thus partially work discipline has no significant effect on productivity (Y). Based on the results of the simultaneous analysis above, it can be seen that the variables of leadership, work environment, ability and work discipline have a significant effect on productivity, while motivation and salary variables have not affected productivity. The largest and most significant regression coefficient is the leadership variable (X_1) of 1.030 which is the variable that has the dominant influence on employee productivity, thus the second hypothesis is rejected.

Leadership is the ability to influence others to carry out tasks in order to achieve the desired goals (Bass & Riggio, 2006). The results of the descriptive analysis show that most of the respondents are hesitant to accept the leadership that is now run or implemented by their superiors. This is due to a lack of communication between superiors and employees in carrying out daily tasks, both formal and non-formal tasks. The formal task relationship is communication between superiors and employees in terms of daily tasks, respondents tend to choose not to agree because the condition is that the boss always orders to work immediately without proper guidance or resource development, in other words not implementing the leadership management function. As for non-formal relationships, namely the relationship between superiors and employees outside of working hours, it is relatively rare because the 1-hour break is used for lunch and there is no canteen where to eat, employees generally eat at home and some employees eat on the edge of the building. So the opportunity to communicate well outside of working hours does not exist. In addition, there is still a lack of supervisory supervision on the implementation of work, as well as supervision of the work of employees, it is necessary to do right way to fix a good supervisory system. The results of the analysis show that leadership has a positive and significant influence on employee productivity, meaning that good leadership will lead to an increase in employee productivity. The task and function of the leader are to direct the behavior of members of the organization to achieve organizational goals, thus the leadership's ability to direct behavior will determine the achievement of employee work productivity. Leadership is a behavioral norm used by a person when he is trying to influence the behavior of others, efforts to harmonize perceptions between people who will influence behavior and those whose behavior will be influenced are very important (Thoha, 2001). A leader must be able to influence his employees so that they can complete their work well, besides that the leader must also know how much employees are willing to take responsibility and motivated to excel. Workability shows the quality of work of employees, where ability is seen from indicators of work mastery and individual contributions as well as task load. Based

on descriptive analysis, it can be seen that most of the employees in the packing department have high abilities, this is mainly supported by the ability of employees to complete the assigned task load. The task load is not a barrier for employees in completing tasks, because almost all employees have a working period of more than 8 years, after 1 year of work the average employee is working smoothly (routinely). However, it turns out that there are still employees who have low abilities and there are still employees who have not mastered their field of work and have not fully contributed both energy and thoughts to their work. This condition is because some employees are still unmarried so their work motivation is not high compared to employees who already have family dependents. Employees who are married tend to work fully and contribute both energy and thought to their work because the work they have has an important meaning. The results of the analysis show that ability has a positive and significant influence on employee productivity, meaning that the higher ability of the employee will lead to an increase in employee productivity. So an employee can achieve satisfactory work productivity depending on his work ability because work ability shows a person's potential to carry out work activities. According to Gibson (1996), workability is a person's potential to carry out tasks. Workability shows a person's skills such as intelligence and skills that are closely related to the physical and mental abilities possessed to carry out work. The absence of this kind of ability can affect employee performance improvement.

Baron (1990) says that every job requires knowledge of certain skills and attitudes to carry out the job well and satisfactorily. High workability, if you have good skills in carrying out assigned tasks, able to handle urgent problems. A good work environment will create a good, comfortable, safe and healthy working atmosphere. Temperature and lighting as well as noise are physical requirements that must be met by companies so that employees who work do not have the impact of experiencing illness due to a bad work environment. The results of the analysis show that the work environment does not affect productivity, meaning that a good work environment will not necessarily lead to high employee productivity. Likewise, assistive devices such as wheelbarrows, buckets and others must be ergonomic, which is a physical facility that supports employee productivity so as not to cause work-related diseases after a long period of work (Tarwaka, 2004). Work discipline is behaviour that is submissive and obedient to company rules, based on the results of the analysis it can be seen that most of the respondents have good work discipline and some do not (Thompson, 2017). However, it turns out that there are still employees who do not agree that they always come and go home on time, this is due to the employee's desire to work overtime so that they get additional income. In addition, there are still employees who do not carry out work in accordance with directions and procedures, this is because employees are skilled, so they have mastered the whole way of working, so even though they use their methods, the results are still good, and can even be completed more quickly. The results of the analysis show that work discipline does not affect productivity.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that the company's productivity level from 2006 to 2009 was unstable (fluctuating) with a declining trend. This situation is caused by inefficient management of input factors or existing resources. The level of labour

utilization also tends to be less efficient, thus causing labour productivity to decline. In addition, production capacity can still be increased by an average of 27.25%. All factors of the level of productivity are due to leadership, and ability. Therefore, to support future productivity improvements to increase the company's competitiveness, the expansion of the selling area is one of the future goals in order to spur the output produced so that the achievement of increasing productivity can be successful. So to support the company's competitiveness, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) must be created and applied as materials to evaluate the efficiency, effectiveness and quality of the products produced for the sake of the production process.

REFERENCES

- Baron, R.A and Greenberg J. 1990. Behaviour in Organization Understanding the Human Side of Work. A Division Siroon and Schuster. Inc. New York.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). Transformational leadership. Psychology press.
- Creswell, John W. 2014. Research Design, Qualitatives, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches (Fourth Edition). United State of America: Sage Publications.
- Gibson, James L. 1982. Organizations Behavior Structure Processes. 4 th ed. Richard D. Irwin Inc.
- Gomes, F.C. 2000. Human Resource Management. Penerbit Andi Offset. Yogyakarta.
- Hughes, R., Ginnett, R. C., & Curphy, G. J. (1993). Leadership. Public Health Nutrition, 12(8), 1029.
- Kuder, G. F., & Richardson, M. W. (1937). The theory of the estimation of test reliability. Psychometrika, 2(3), 151-160.
- Kuehn, A. A., & Day, R. L. (1962). Strategy of product quality. Harvard Business Review.
- Nurgiyantoro, B. 2000. Applied Statistics for Social Sciences Research. Cetakan Pertama. Penerbit Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Plag, I. (2020). Productivity. The handbook of English linguistics, 483-499.
- Shepard, L. A. (1993). Chapter 9: Evaluating test validity. Review of research in education, 19(1), 405-450.
- Sumanth, J. David, 1984, Productivity Engineering And Management: Productivity Measurement in Manufacturing and Service Organisation, McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Tarwaka., Solichul. H.A. Bakri., Lilik Sudiajeng. 2004. Ergonomics for Occupational Safety, Health and Productivity. Penerbit Hiperkes. Surakarta.
- Thoha, Mifta, 2001. Organizational Behavior Basic Concepts and Applications. CV. Rajawali, Jakarta.
- Thompson, E. P. (2017). Time, work-discipline, and industrial capitalism. Class: The Anthology, 27-40.